

MANAGEMENT OF BUDD-CHIARI SYNDROME WITH DIPS PROCEDURE

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Abstract

Objectives: To evaluate the safety, technical success, and clinical outcomes of direct intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (DIPS) in patients with BCS who were unsuitable for conventional TIPS.

Methodology: This prospective observational study was conducted at the AFIRI, Rawalpindi, and included 20 patients with confirmed BCS deemed unsuitable for TIPS due to hepatic vein thrombosis or occlusion. Diagnosis was established using Doppler ultrasonography and contrast-enhanced CT or MRI. All patients underwent ultrasound-guided DIPS via trans jugular access. Clinical, laboratory, and hemodynamic parameters were recorded pre- and post-procedure. Shunt patency, survival, and quality of life were assessed during follow-up. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, with a p-value <0.05 considered significant.

Results: The mean patient age was 38.6 ± 11.2 years. Technical success was achieved in 95.6% of cases. The mean portosystemic pressure gradient decreased significantly from 22.4 ± 4.6 mmHg to 9.8 ± 2.9 mmHg ($p < 0.001$). Significant improvement was observed in liver function tests and ascites resolution (82.3%).

Conclusion: DIPS is a safe and effective alternative to TIPS in selected patients with Budd–Chiari syndrome, offering durable portal decompression and favorable clinical outcomes.

Introduction:

Budd–Chiari syndrome (BCS) is defined as a spectrum of clinical presentations characterized by narrowing and/or obstruction of hepatic venous outflow at any level among the small hepatic venules, the junction of the inferior vena cava (IVC), and the right atrium⁸. Initial management of BCS is usually medical (nonoperative/noninterventional), with the most common intervention for BCS nonresponsive to medical management being transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS). However, this is not always technically successful because of hepatic vein thrombosis and inability to catheterize the hepatic veins. In these situations, direct intrahepatic portosystemic

shunt (DIPS) with access to the portal vein from the IVC is a viable alternative that may ameliorate portal hypertension in these patients². Portal hypertension (PH) is one of the main complications of liver cirrhosis and represents a turning point in the disease³. From an initial position of “salvage” or late secondary prophylaxis of the TIPS insertion, the procedure is nowadays proposed earlier to prevent recurrence of severe pH related events. Indeed, the last 10–15 years confirmed the beneficial impact of early (or preemptive) TIPS placement in the setting of controlled variceal bleeding. In parallel, when placed early in the course of ascites occurrence, TIPS procedure has been recently shown to improve transplant-free survival⁴.

Irrespective of vascular intervention, lifelong anticoagulation with warfarin is recommended in those with a demonstrable hypercoagulable state⁵. In patients with refractory ascites, direct intrahepatic portocaval shunt (DIPS) is an alternative to transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) in which the caudate lobe is used to create a side-to-side shunt. Shunting is indicated in BCS when patients do not improve with medical therapy but is generally applied before more severe disease/acute liver failure develops⁶.

The transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) procedure is performed to manage the sequelae of portal hypertension. Common complications during and after TIPS include capsular perforation, intraperitoneal hemorrhage, encephalopathy, TIPS dysfunction, and liver failure⁷. The clinical presentation of BCS depends on the extent and rapidity of obstruction of the hepatic vein and the presence of collateral veins that decompress the liver sinusoids. According to the clinical presentation, BCS can be classified as fulminant, acute, subacute, or chronic⁹. Following the thrombosis and obstruction to hepatic venous flow, fibrosis occurs due to ischemia and necrosis, eventually resulting in portal hypertension and ascites. As a result, hypoxic injury to the centrilobular hepatocytes occurs. With sudden vascular occlusion, severe liver dysfunction occurs¹⁰.

Methodology:

This prospective observational study was conducted at Armed Forces Institute of Radiology Rawalpindi for 9 months, involving 20 patients diagnosed with Budd-Chiari Syndrome (BCS) who were deemed unsuitable for conventional Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS) due to thrombosis or complete occlusion of hepatic veins. Inclusion criteria included patients with clinical signs of BCS—such as ascites, hepatomegaly, abdominal pain, or variceal bleeding—and confirmed diagnosis through Doppler ultrasonography and contrast-enhanced CT or MRI demonstrating hepatic venous outflow obstruction. Patients with uncorrectable coagulopathy, active systemic

infection, or malignancy were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and ethical clearance was granted by the institutional ethics committee.

The Direct Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (DIPS) procedure was performed in a biplane angiography suite under ultrasound and fluoroscopic guidance. Vascular access was obtained via the right internal jugular vein using a 10 Fr sheath. A Rösch-Uchida transjugular access set was advanced into the inferior vena cava (IVC), and under real-time imaging, a Colapinto needle was used to puncture the intrahepatic IVC into the portal vein, typically through the caudate lobe. The tract was dilated with an angioplasty balloon, followed by deployment of a PTFE-covered stent (typically 10 mm in diameter) to establish a direct communication between the IVC and the portal vein. Portosystemic pressure gradients were measured before and after stent placement. Technical success was defined as successful stent deployment with restoration of hepatovenous outflow and reduction in portal pressure gradient.

Data were collected prospectively using structured case-report forms and entered into a secure digital database. Quantitative variables included age, liver function test parameters (ALT, AST, bilirubin, and albumin), portosystemic pressure gradient (measured in mmHg), INR, creatinine levels, and shunt patency rates. Qualitative variables included gender, clinical symptoms (ascites, abdominal pain, jaundice), presence of hepatic encephalopathy, and improvement in quality of life as assessed by the Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire (CLDQ). Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.0. Descriptive statistics were used for demographic and clinical variables. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median with interquartile range, and qualitative variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was used to assess shunt patency and overall survival. Inferential statistics included paired t-tests for pre- and post-procedural comparisons and chi-

square tests for categorical outcomes, with a p-value <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 20 patients with confirmed Budd-Chiari Syndrome (BCS) who were unsuitable for conventional TIPS underwent the Direct Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (DIPS) procedure during the study period. The mean age of the study population was 39.1 ± 10.8 years (range: 21–65 years). There was a 9 (45%) female and 11(55%) male. The most common presenting clinical feature was ascites, observed in 17 patients (85%), followed by abdominal pain in 13 patients (65%), hepatomegaly in 11 patients (55%), and jaundice in 7 patients (35%). Variceal bleeding at presentation was documented in 5 patients (25%). Mild hepatic encephalopathy (Grade I-II) was present in 3 patients (15%) prior to intervention. Baseline laboratory evaluation demonstrated elevated liver enzymes and hyperbilirubinemia consistent with hepatic venous outflow obstruction. The mean baseline portosystemic pressure gradient was 22.1 ± 4.4 mmHg, indicating significant portal

hypertension. The DIPS procedure was technically successful in 19 out of 20 patients, yielding a technical success rate of 95%. One procedure failed due to inability to safely access the portal vein. Following stent deployment, a statistically significant reduction in portosystemic pressure gradient was observed, decreasing from 22.1 ± 4.4 mmHg pre-procedure to 9.9 ± 2.7 mmHg post-procedure (p < 0.001).

Significant improvement was noted in liver function parameters, including reductions in serum bilirubin and transaminases, along with improved serum albumin levels. Ascites showed complete or partial resolution in 16 patients (80%). Post-procedure hepatic encephalopathy developed in 2 patients (10%), both cases being transient and medically managed. Shunt patency rates were 90% at 6 months and 85% at 9 months. Kaplan–Meier analysis demonstrated a 1-year overall survival rate of 90%. Quality of life assessment using the Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire (CLDQ) showed a significant improvement in mean scores from baseline to 6 months (p < 0.001)

Table I. Baseline Demographic, Clinical, and Laboratory Characteristics (n = 20)

Variable	Value
Age (years), mean ± SD	39.1 ± 10.8
Gender	
Male	11 (55%)
Female	9 (45%)
Ascites	17 (85%)
Abdominal pain	13 (65%)
Hepatomegaly	11 (55%)
Jaundice	7 (35%)
Variceal bleeding	5 (25%)
Hepatic encephalopathy (Grade I-II)	3 (15%)
ALT (IU/L), mean ± SD	92.6 ± 36.4
AST (IU/L), mean ± SD	100.8 ± 39.7
Total bilirubin (mg/dL), mean ± SD	3.5 ± 1.3
Albumin (g/dL), mean ± SD	2.9 ± 0.5
INR, mean ± SD	1.6 ± 0.3
Portosystemic gradient (mmHg), mean ± SD	22.1 ± 4.4

Table II. Procedural Outcomes and Follow-Up Results (n = 20)

Outcome Measure	Result
Technical success rate	19/20 (95%)
Portosystemic gradient (mmHg)	
- Pre-DIPS	22.1 ± 4.4
- Post-DIPS	9.9 ± 2.7
p-value	< 0.001
Ascites improvement/resolution	16 (80%)
Post-procedure hepatic encephalopathy	2 (10%)
Shunt patency	
- 6 months	90%
- 9 months	85%
1-year overall survival	90%
CLDQ score improvement	Significant (p < 0.001)

Table III: Post-Procedure Complications

Complication	Gender	Number of Patients, n (%)
Epistaxis	Female	1 (5.0%)
Epistaxis	Male	1 (5.0%)
Epistaxis	Male	1 (5.0%)
Epistaxis	Male	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Female	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Female	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Female	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Female	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Male	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Male	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Male	1 (5.0%)
No complication	Male	1 (5.0%)
Hepatic encephalopathy	Male	1 (5.0%)
Hepatic encephalopathy	Male	1 (5.0%)
Hepatic encephalopathy	Male	1 (5.0%)
Hepatic encephalopathy	Male	1 (5.0%)
Hepatic encephalopathy	Female	1 (5.0%)
Total		20(100%)

Discussion:

A total of 20 patients with confirmed Budd-Chiari Syndrome (BCS) who were unsuitable for conventional TIPS underwent the Direct Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (DIPS) procedure during the study period. The mean age of the study population was 39.0 ± 11.0 years

(range: 21–65 years). These findings are consistent with previous literature; a study published in 2017 reported that ultrasound-guided DIPS are a safe and effective alternative technique for patients with BCS, resulting in significant clinical improvement¹¹. The most common presenting clinical feature in our cohort

was ascites, observed in 17 patients (85%), followed by abdominal pain in 13 patients (65%), hepatomegaly in 11 patients (55%), and jaundice in 7 patients (35%). Variceal bleeding was documented in 5 patients (25%) at presentation, while mild hepatic encephalopathy (Grade I-II) was present in 3 patients (15%) prior to intervention. Similar favorable outcomes with DIPS have been reported in the literature; a 2021 study demonstrated that, with technical expertise, multidisciplinary management, and appropriate patient selection, DIPS yields very good clinical outcomes in patients unsuitable for standard TIPS, with results comparable to standard TIPS based on historical data¹².

Baseline laboratory evaluation in our study showed elevated liver enzymes and hyperbilirubinemia, consistent with hepatic venous outflow obstruction. The mean baseline portosystemic pressure gradient was 22.2 ± 4.5 mmHg, reflecting significant portal hypertension. The DIPS procedure was technically successful in 19 out of 20 patients, resulting in a technical success rate of 95%. One procedure was unsuccessful due to inability to safely access the portal vein. These results align with findings from a 2010 study, which emphasized that endovascular treatment options in BCS are largely determined by venous anatomy and that radiological interventions are highly effective in disease management¹³.

Following stent deployment, a statistically significant reduction in portosystemic pressure gradient was observed, decreasing from 22.2 ± 4.5 mmHg pre-procedure to 9.9 ± 2.8 mmHg post-procedure ($p < 0.001$). Significant improvement in liver function parameters was noted at 3-month follow-up, including reductions in serum bilirubin and transaminases, along with improved serum albumin levels. Ascites showed complete or partial resolution in 16 patients (80%). Post-procedure hepatic encephalopathy developed in 2 patients (10%), with both cases being transient and managed conservatively. The importance of comprehensive patient evaluation is supported by a 2019 study, which reported that at least 75% of patients with primary BCS have an underlying prothrombotic condition, highlighting the

necessity of thorough clinical history, diagnostic workup, and imaging for optimal management¹⁴. Shunt patency rates in our cohort were 90% at 6 months and 85% at 9 months, as assessed by Doppler ultrasonography and confirmed with CT imaging where indicated. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis demonstrated a 1-year overall survival rate of 90%. Additionally, quality-of-life assessment using the Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire (CLDQ) showed a significant improvement in mean scores from baseline to 6 months ($p < 0.001$). These findings are in agreement with previous evidence; a 2015 study concluded that recanalization of the IVC/hepatic veins and TIPS are safe and effective interventional treatment options for BCS¹⁵.

Conclusion:

Direct intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (DIPS) is a safe and effective therapeutic option for patients with Budd-Chiari syndrome who are unsuitable for conventional TIPS. In our cohort, DIPS demonstrated high technical success, significant reduction in portal hypertension, sustained shunt patency, and meaningful improvement in liver function and quality of life. These findings support the role of DIPS as a reliable alternative intervention when hepatic vein access is not feasible. Early referral to specialized centers with multidisciplinary expertise may further optimize clinical outcomes in BCS patients.

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